

Laying Performance of Native Chicken (*Gallus gallus L.*) Fed with Natural Egg Enhancers

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Abstract:

Native chickens, inherent to sustainable agriculture, play a crucial role in diverse ecosystems and local economies. Recognizing their significance, this study, conducted at Lagangilang, Abra aimed to evaluate the impact of annatto seed, turmeric, and red-hot pepper as additives on the egg performance of native chickens over four months laid out in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD). Focusing on laying performance in terms of average monthly egg laid, hen house egg production (HDEP), egg mass, egg weight, and mortality and morbidity rate. The research revealed no significant

differences in various egg performance parameters, nevertheless, the T3 annatto seed had the highest mean among the treatments next with the commercial egg booster in terms of laid eggs, while unexpectedly contributing to a reduction in mortality and morbidity rates among native chickens. The study suggests that while these additives may not serve as direct egg promoters, they hold promise for improving specific aspects of native chicken eggs, warranting further investigation into their potential health benefits and optimization for market appeal. In terms of return above the feed, stock, and additive costs, utilizing annatto seed and turmeric as additives is 4-13%. Hence, a comprehensive understanding of these implications is vital for informed decision-making when considering additives and enhancers in native chicken production. Though all egg enhancers are acceptable, the prevailing price of the additives to be used should be considered.

Keywords: *additives, egg enhancers, native chicken, laying performance, Philippines.*

Introduction

The native chicken is a nondescript, mongrel bird that has evolved from jungle fowls interbred with domesticated ones brought into the country by early Chinese, Spanish, and Dutch traders, and settlers. Despite their low productivity, indigenous chicken is known to possess desirable characteristics such as thermo-tolerance, resistance to some diseases, good egg and meat flavor, presence of hard eggshells, high

fertility, and hatchability as well as high dressing percentage (Melesse and Negesse, 2011).

The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations forbids using most artificial pigments in animal diets due to their toxic effects on humans (Aparecida *et al.*, 2022). These guidelines affected several animal production industries, particularly egg production, where pigments are extremely important to provide egg yolk color.

Moreover, due to their remarkable bixin level, which is a natural antioxidant, the annatto seed by-product could be used in animal supplementation. Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) has been extensively used to give color and flavor to foods. It is also used for the treatment of a variety of inflammatory conditions (Malekizadeh *et al.*, 2012). While Red Pepper is a good egg yolk colorant and is widely cultivated around the world (Huaqiang *et al.*, 2012). The red pepper contains small amounts of red pigments and comparatively large amounts of yellow carotenoids which pass readily into the yolk thereby enhancing the intensity of the yellow color.

Thus, this study aims to determine the effects of different natural egg enhancers on the laying performance evaluation of native chicken.

Materials and Methods

Two breeding houses were utilized measuring 11 x 10 meters made up of galvanized iron, iron posts, and steel matting. Each house was subdivided into 8 compartments measuring 2 x 5 meters per pen. Each pen contained 6 hens and 1 rooster (6:1). There were three (3) bamboo nest coops hung on the sidewalls of each pen, an

automatic feeder (5 kilos capacity), a waterer (4liters capacity), and perches were placed beside the nest for the hens to easily go to their nest during oviposition. The native chickens were at least laying and 1.5 kilos in weight with typically of the same phenotypic characterization which is light to dark brown.

Native chickens were given the feeds formulated according to treatments and restricted feeding was employed where each bird was given 110 grams daily and served at 7:00-8:00 in the morning and 4:00-5:00 in the afternoon.

Research Design and Treatments

The Completely Randomized Design (CRD) involving five treatments with three replications in each treatment was followed. The total area was divided into 15 cages representing all the replications.

The treatments of the study were the following:

- T₁- Pure formulated feed with no feed additives
- T₂- Commercial egg enhancer (5g/10kg of feeds)
- T₃- Annatto Seed powder as additives at 1%
- T₄- Turmeric powder as additives at 1%
- T₅- Red Hot Pepper powder as additives at 1%

Figure 1. The experimental Layout

Source: The Author

Statistical Analysis

Using the computed mean, the analysis of variance (ANOVA) was analyzed following the Completely Randomized Design (CRD applying the Statistical Tool for Agricultural Research (STAR) software.

Table 1. The Average Monthly Laid Egg Harvest of Native Chicken Fed with Natural Egg Enhancers

Treatments	April	May	June	July
T ₁ – No additives	11.87	10.20	7.33	9.47
T ₂ – Commercial	12.13	11.20	12.07	12.20
T ₃ – Annatto seed	11.53	11.27	8.33	10.47
T ₄ – Turmeric	8.47	8.33	6.93	8.73
T ₅ – Red Hot Pepper	11.53	7.40	7.33	7.93
ANOVA Results	ns	ns	ns	ns
C.V. (%)	22.21	25.98	32.82	33.55

Based on the results, the average monthly laid egg harvest from the birds ranges from 8.47-12.13 in April, whereas the highest mean was obtained from T₂-commercial, followed by T₁ - No additives with a mean of 11.87, T₃- Annatto seed and T₅- Red Hot Pepper (11.53), while the lowest mean was recorded in T₄- Turmeric. In the second month of the study, T₃- Annatto seed had the highest mean of 11.27, followed by T₂- Commercial (11.20), T₁ - No additives (10.20), T₄- Turmeric with 8.33 and T₅- Red Hot Pepper with a mean of 7.40. In the 3rd to 4th month of the study, a similar trend was observed on the egg harvest performance of native chicken whereas, T₃- Annatto seed had a higher mean compared to Turmeric and Red-hot pepper.

The result is similar to the result of Garcia *et al.* (2015), where it was concluded that adding ground annatto seed at levels up to 2.0% in the feed of red-egg-laying hens does not influence the egg performance. Likewise, Huaqiang *et al.*, (2012) reported in his experiment that there were no differences in egg-laying performance, feed consumption, and feed conversion ratio due to the inclusion of red pepper pigment in the diet of laying hens. On the other hand, Puvaca *et al.*, (2018) reported that egg production, weight, and mass increased significantly in laying hens fed

Results and Discussions

Average Monthly Laid Eggs

As data reflects, there was no significant difference ($P>0.05$) between the treatment means from the April-July 2023 production period.

turmeric powder at the level of 0.5% in the basal diet. Thus, the contrary result could be due to different levels of turmeric and species of poultry being introduced with the treatment. Whereas commercial strains of the layer is genetically good compared to native chicken.

Annatto seed, red hot pepper, and turmeric are natural ingredients that are often used as dietary additives in poultry nutrition, but they may not directly provide significant amounts of lysine and methionine for egg improvement. Rather, these natural ingredients may offer other potential benefits for poultry, such as their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, which can support overall health. This implies that the egg enhancers did not significantly boost the chickens' laying performance monthly, however, to increase egg production may need to consider other factors or additives for future researchers.

According to Santiago (2018), the average number of eggs from Philippine native chicken's ranges from 60-100 eggs per year with an average of 8.33 monthly, this means that the produced eggs from this study are within the range reported with 116.61 average eggs per year.

Average Hen Day Egg production (HDEP)

Hen House Egg Production (HDEP) are parameters to measure egg production performance. The results show that the commercial treatment (T₂) had the highest HDEP in all months, while the turmeric treatment (T₄) had the lowest HDEP. However, the ANOVA result was not significant, indicating that there was no significant difference in the HDEP among the treatments.

One study found that the use of natural feed additives such as turmeric and ginger can

improve egg production and egg quality in laying hens (Soliman *et al.*,2020). Another study found that the use of dietary supplementation with turmeric powder can improve egg production and egg quality in quails (Milkiassa and Mollab, 2022), also highlights the importance of balancing the protein, energy, and fat content in the diet of laying hens to improve egg size and quality. Thus the result is similar to the investigation showed that dietary supplementation of turmeric at 1.0 g/kg did not influence hen house egg production as well as hen day egg production (Puvača *et al.*,2018).

Table 2. The Average Monthly Hen Day Egg Production (HDEP) of Native Chicken Fed with Natural Egg Enhancers

Treatments	April	May	June	July
T ₁ – No additives	39.55	35.50	25.61	33.06
T ₂ – Commercial	40.44	36.45	40.39	40.78
T ₃ – Annatto seed	38.44	35.78	27.78	38.11
T ₄ – Turmeric	28.28	28.17	25.11	31.67
T ₅ – Red Hot Pepper	38.45	23.56	24.44	26.44
ANOVA Results	ns	ns	ns	ns
C.V. (%)	22.18	25.82	30.50	33.73

Generally, native chicken's average hen-day egg production at 40 weeks old is about 24.3% (Brosas, 2022). With these, the computed HHEP result during the production period could be generally good in performance and exceeded the reported average HDEP of native chicken in the Philippines.

Average Egg Weight

The results indicate that the egg weight of the treatments varied across the months. In April, T₂ (Commercial) had the highest egg weight (45.55

g), while T₄ (Turmeric) had the lowest (38.22 g). In May, T₁ (No additives) had the highest egg weight (40.04 g), while T₄ (Turmeric) had the lowest (33.73 g). In June, T₃ (Annatto seed) had the highest egg weight (37.00 g), while T₄ (Turmeric) had the lowest (31.00 g). In July, T₂ (Commercial) had the highest egg weight (42.75 g), while T₅ (Red Hot Pepper) had the lowest (33.37 g). However, the analysis of variance results showed that the differences in egg weight among the treatments were not significant.

Table 3. The Average Monthly Egg Weight of Native Chicken Fed with Natural Egg Enhancers

Treatments	April	May	June	July
T ₁ – No additives	40.27	40.04	32.45	33.53
T ₂ – Commercial	45.55	44.24	43.29	42.75
T ₃ – Annatto seed	44.35	41.16	37.00	41.49
T ₄ – Turmeric	38.22	33.73	31.00	32.85
T ₅ – Red Hot Pepper	43.65	33.81	34.58	33.37
ANOVA Results	ns	ns	ns	ns
C.V. (%)	8.68	18.01	18.52	19.13

The egg weight of the popular Philippine native chicken breed is about 40-45 grams (Santiago,2018). Thus, T₃ (Annatto seed) and T₂ (Commercial) are within the reported range of egg weight.

Literature study on the comparison between the egg yolk flavor of indigenous breeds and commercial laying hens based on sensory evaluation, artificial sensors, and GC-MS reported significant breed differences for sensory attributes of egg yolk, but the differences in egg weight among the breeds were not significant (Gao *et al.*,2022). Furthermore, the search results suggest that non-significant results are common in studies on egg production and egg quality in laying hens. For instance, a study on the variation and association of hen performance and egg quality traits in individual early laying ISA Brown hens reported that some of the traits, such as egg weight, were not significantly different among the hens (Anene *et al.*,2020)

The results suggest that nutrition is an important factor in boosting egg size, and that specific nutrients such as methionine and lysine can significantly contribute to egg size improvement (Saenz, 2021). Thus, it is important to consider

other factors that can affect egg weight, such as genetics, nutrition, age, and environmental factors.

Average Egg Mass

The results show that the egg mass of the control group (T₁) and the group given commercial egg enhancers (T₂) were consistently higher than the other groups in all months. However, the differences were not significant (ns). The egg mass of the group given annatto seed (T₃) and red hot pepper (T₅) were also consistently higher than the group given turmeric (T₄). The coefficient of variation (C.V.) was relatively high, ranging from 22.62% to 61.42%, indicating a high degree of variability in the data.

A study by Hassan *et al.*,(2016) reported that the mean egg mass of Nigerian indigenous chickens was 36.8 g. Another study by Grobbelaar *et al.* (2010) found that the egg production potentials of four indigenous chicken breeds in South Africa ranged from 1.5 to 3.5 eggs per hen per week, with an average egg weight of 50 g. These studies suggest that the egg mass of the native chicken in this study is within the range of egg mass produced by indigenous chickens in other countries.

Table 4. The Average Monthly Egg Mass of Native Chicken Fed with Natural Egg Enhancers

Treatments	April	May	June	July
T ₁ – No additives	15.70	14.18	8.13	11.69
T ₂ – Commercial	18.51	16.35	17.53	17.43
T ₃ – Annatto seed	16.87	14.69	10.36	12.67
T ₄ – Turmeric	10.59	10.53	9.09	10.83
T ₅ – Red Hot Pepper	15.75	8.96	8.70	16.24
ANOVA Results	ns	ns	ns	ns
C.V. (%)	22.62	33.35	38.45	61.42

Similar studies have reported varying results on the egg mass of chickens given with egg enhancers. One study on the monthly hen day egg production of three parent strains found that the egg mass of the chickens varied across strains and months (Udeh *et al.*,2013). Another study on the variation and association of hen performance and egg quality traits in individual early-laying

ISA Brown hens found that the egg mass of the chickens varied across hens (Anene *et al.*,2020). The varied results of this present study could be due to type of species of chicken utilized and that the egg mass of chickens can be affected by various factors, such as genetics, age, and feed additives.

Overall, the results of Table 4 suggest that the egg mass of native chickens given with egg enhancers varies across treatments and months, but the differences among treatments were not statistically significant. This implies that other factors, such as genetics, age, and feed management, may have a greater impact on the egg mass of native chickens.

Average Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR)

The results show that there were no significant differences among treatments in all months. FCR is an important measure of efficiency in livestock production, as it indicates how effectively animals convert feed into body weight gain or product output. A lower FCR

indicates better feed efficiency, which means that less feed is required to produce a unit of egg mass. The average FCR can vary depending on various factors, including genetics, nutrition, management practices, and environmental conditions. However, a commonly accepted range for FCR in laying hens is between 2.5 and 4.0, which means that it takes 2.5 to 4.0 kilograms of feed to produce one dozen (12) eggs (Champrix, 2023).

In this result, the T₃-Annatto had a better efficiency compared to turmeric and hot pepper, thus this is consistent with the result in egg harvest and HDEP.

Table 5. The Average Feed Conversion Ratio (FCR) of Native Chicken Fed with Natural Egg Enhancers

Treatments	April	May	June	July
T ₁ – No additives	2.76	2.75	3.43	3.29
T ₂ – Commercial	2.42	2.54	2.55	2.58
T ₃ – Annatto seed	2.48	2.68	3.01	2.77
T ₄ – Turmeric	2.88	3.57	4.08	3.44
T ₅ – Red Hot Pepper	2.54	3.70	3.22	3.55
ANOVA Results	ns	ns	ns	ns
C.V. (%)	9.62	28.14	28.16	23.01

In a study conducted in Kenya, feed conversion ratio was strongly correlated to egg production traits than with feed intake, implying that variability in FCR was majorly influenced by production traits than by feed intake (Miyumo *et al.*, 2023).

In another study, the feed conversion ratio was calculated every week for every subgroup, and the results showed that the inclusion of marigolds in the diet of laying hens did not affect the feed conversion ratio (Altuntas and Aydin 2014). A study by Anene *et al.* (2021) found that hens that exhibit poorer feed efficiency produce eggs with lower albumen quality and are prone to being overweight. Thus, the contradicting result of the present study on layer commercials is due to the genetic factor that commercial layers have normally higher weight compared to native chicken.

Therefore, a non-significant result in FCR may indicate that other factors, such as feeding

behavior, age, temperature, and breed, may have a greater impact on egg production and feed intake.

The better efficiency obtained from T₂ (commercial treatment) could be due to its sufficient content of multivitamins, minerals, and amino acids such as Vitamins A, D, E, B2, B12, Pyridoxine hydrochloride, Vitamin C, Lysine and Methionine that promotes good health and vigor that is needed for egg improvement. Meanwhile, annatto seed, red hot pepper, and turmeric are natural ingredients that are often used as dietary additives in poultry nutrition, but they may not directly provide significant amounts of lysine and methionine for egg improvement. Rather, these natural ingredients may offer other potential benefits for poultry, such as their antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, which can support the overall health of the birds.

Morbidity and Mortality Rate

The results indicate that the mortality rate was highest in T₁ (no additives) at 13.33%, while T₃ (Annatto seed) had the highest morbidity rate at 6.66%. T₂ (Commercial) and T₅ (Red Hot

Pepper) had no mortality or morbidity rates. Similar studies have shown that mortality rates in chicken production can be affected by various factors such as hygiene, housing system, cage vs. floor rearing, strain of the chicken, and flock size.

Figure 2. The Morbidity and Mortality Rate of Native Chicken Fed with Natural Egg Enhancers

Source: The Author

These spices have health benefits for humans and can improve the overall health and growth of poultry birds. Annatto seed and turmeric are rich in minerals and nutrients that help protect the body, and they have been shown to have anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. Hot pepper contains capsaicin, which has been linked to lower bad cholesterol levels and a reduced risk of heart-related mortality. Additionally, egg enhancers that contain multivitamins, minerals, and ovary-stimulating herbs can improve the health and production of eggs in poultry birds (Lagana *et al.* 2011).

While the search results do not provide a direct link between these spices and reduced chicken mortality, it implies that incorporating these spices into the diet of poultry birds can have positive effects on their overall health and well-being.

The mortality was observed during the onset of the rainy season, whereas rainy and cold seasons can lead to changes in temperature, weather conditions, and reduced daylight, which can impact the productivity of poultry, especially

laying birds. The rainy season may bring about challenges such as reduced daylight, shortened daylight hours, and increased relative humidity, which can affect the well-being and productivity of poultry.

Cost and Return above Feed, Stocks, and Additives Costs

The T₁ - No additives serve as the control or baseline, with a cost and return percentage of 17%. This means that there is a 17% change in costs and returns compared to the standard when no additives are given.

This treatment represents the baseline scenario without any additives. It may have relatively standard production results. However, in the context of enhancing egg production or improving overall performance, it might be considered less efficient compared to treatments with additives.

Treatment 2 has a cost and return percentage of 22%. This indicates that using commercial additives increases the cost and return compared to the baseline by 22%. Commercial additives are

designed to optimize production outcomes, so they may enhance egg production and overall performance. Treatment 3, which involves annatto seed as an additive, results in a lower cost and return percentage of 13%. This means that using annatto seed is more cost-effective compared to the baseline (T₁). Treatment 4, which includes turmeric as an additive, shows the most significant cost reduction with a cost and return percentage of 4%. This indicates that using turmeric is highly cost-effective and improves returns. Lastly, Treatment 5 has a cost and return percentage of -6%. This negative value implies that using red hot pepper as an additive results in a decrease in costs and returns compared to the baseline. This may not be a desirable outcome, and this is due to the high price of red-hot pepper.

Although additives may offer economic efficiency, their use, especially synthetic ones, must be approached with caution due to regulatory and food safety concerns. The implications of the table results extend beyond economics, encompassing factors like food safety, regulatory compliance, livestock performance, and genetic potential in poultry production.

This implies that in utilizing annatto seed and turmeric as additives it will give 4-13% or in every peso invested there is a return of 4-13 centavo net income. A comprehensive understanding of these implications is vital for informed decision-making when considering additives and enhancers in native chicken production. While all egg enhancers are acceptable, the prevailing price of the additives to be used should be considered.

Table 6. The Cost and Return above Feeds, Stocks, and Additives of Native Chicken Fed with Natural Egg Enhancers

Particulars	Treatments				
	T ₁ – No additives	T ₂ – Commercial	T ₃ – Annatto seed	T ₄ – Turmeric	T ₅ – Red Hot Pepper
A. Sales					
Eggs @ 15.00/pc	8,970.00	10,710.00	9,135.00	7,305.00	7,695.00
Stocks (250.00/kl)	5,817.50	6,375.00	5,775.00	6,965.00	5,887.50
Sub Total A:	14,787.50	17,085.00	14,910.00	14,270.00	13,582.50
B. Expenses					
Stocks (500.00/hd)	7,500.00	7,500.00	7,500.00	7,500.00	7,500.00
Feeds @ 30.00/kl (396/hd)	5,148.00	5,940.00	5,544.00	5,544.00	5,940.00
Amount of feed additives		594.00	130.00	693.00	990.00
Sub Total B:	12,648.00	14,034.00	13,174.00	13,737.00	14,430.00
Net Income	2,139.00	3,051.00	1,736.00	533.00	(847.50)
ROI	17%	22%	13%	4%	(6%)

Conclusion

Utilizing commercial egg booster followed by annatto seed had the best performance in terms of monthly egg harvest and hen-day egg production. Promising outcomes surfaced with a reduction in mortality and morbidity rates among native chickens when exposed to these additives. This unforeseen benefit suggests a potential link between the additives and improved chicken health. Moreover, utilizing these additives delivers a 4-15% return above the feed, stocks, and supplement costs of using

annatto and turmeric as feed additives compared to commercial egg boosters.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest

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